

ISic1395

I.Sicily inscription 1395

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

marble (white)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140902

1. νεωτέρα ΣΚΑΤΑΚΑΤ[η]Α... Ἀ[ρ]χύτα [ς]

2. ΝΣΤιοδώρου {²⁷[Ε]στιοδ.....ώρου (Wilamowitz)}²⁷

Σάν[τρ]α τὸν ναὸν καὶ τὸ

3. ἄγαλμα ἐπόεισε

4. ἐκ τῶν ιδίων.

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493010

EDCS 39101522

PHI 140902

Bibliography

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Manganaro, G. 1963. Nuove ricerche di epigrafia siceliota. *Siculorum Gymnasium*. 16: 51-64. At 53-54
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